

Numerical Simulation of combustor for biogas gasification

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ABSTRACT

These days, gasification is regarded as a globally accepted method for sustainably producing energy from leftovers. Its outcome is a synthetic gas that may be utilized for various purposes, including electricity generation, heat production, and the production of fuels. This process is very important and has several uses, helping with waste management and energy generation. The application of computational fluid dynamics (CFD) aids in comprehending the complicated gasification process by estimating the ideal parameters that must be used to obtain the best syngas for the intended application. In this study, a numerical model of a combustor is developed. The reaction mechanism and stoichiometry were produced from the coal calculator by the proximal and ultimate input of the feed given, and the species transport model in Fluent was used by combining all the zones of the combustor. The contour of the mole fraction of O₂, CO₂ and H₂O is shown. The temperature contour of the gasifier model along with the coal mass concentration is also been determined. This study can further investigate different types of gasifiers by changing the reaction and substituting for the standard gasifier reaction. Also, numerous proximate and ultimate analyses derived from various feeds and biomass can be assigned.

KEYWORDS: *Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), Gasifier, Combustor, Simulation, Mole Fraction.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Fossil fuels are primarily used to meet the rising energy demand to meet the comfort and financial demands of modern civilization. This is an environmental issue since the extraction and conversion of fossil fuels destroy the planet's natural resources, release harmful greenhouse gases, harm living things, and damage the built environment and cultural legacy. A solution to these circumstances is the conversion of various feedstocks, such as trash, biomass, or even their mixes, which allows for the sustainable generation of energy from materials that are prone to disposal (Ramos et al., 2019). Gasification offers a renewable alternative to fossil fuel-based power generation. Gasification is a thermo-chemical partial oxidation process that has enormous promise for recovering biomass energy since it can turn biomass into biochar, which has a significant potential for conserving carbon, and combustible gases, such as syngas, which may then be further transformed into electricity and heat (Wan et al., 2018). To put it briefly, gasification contributes to a more sustainable energy future by providing a flexible and perhaps cleaner method of using different carbon-based resources. The rapid development of gasification technology is restricted by the slow and costly nature of conventional experiment-based gasifier design techniques. In terms of cost and safety, experiment-based approaches are highly unsuitable for industrial-scale gasification systems. In the present scenario, different approaches to designing and optimizing gasification systems are offered by modeling-based techniques, such as mathematical models and computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulation (Wan et al., 2018).

Pandey et al. (2022) developed a 2-D axisymmetric steady-state computational fluid dynamics (CFD) model for biomass gasification in a fixed bed Imbert downdraft gasifier. The gasifier with a capacity of around 5 kW is subjected to a discrete phase model (DPM) based on the Euler-Lagrangian method with species movement. DPM is used for the particle-continuous phase interaction to depict more realistic gasification events. By using a different chemical kinetic approach to investigate the different gasification parameters, the suggested model aims to advance the CFD technique. The model is verified at a few

equivalency ratios (0.19-0.33) for producer gas composition and found to be more consistent with experimental results found in the literature. Gasifier and combustor reactors use various fluidization regimes, resulting in varying flow patterns and solid phase dispersion coefficients. The higher parts of both reactors exhibit high particle heat transfer coefficients due to intense reactions (Sun et al.,2023). In this industrial-scale device, sand in the combustor has a higher time-averaged heat transfer coefficient than gasifier sand by around 40 W/(m²K). The particle-level findings might be helpful for industrial operations using biomass steam-gasification processes. Large eddy simulation along with a multiphase particle-in-cell technique is used to numerically simulate the dense gas-solid reactive flow in a pilot-scale dual fluidized bed for biomass gasification (Wan et al.,2020). The large mass percentage of low-temperature steam in the gasifier results in a high gas phase specific heat capacity and thermal conductivity. A significant mass percentage of gaseous species is produced in the right section of the gasifier by the biomass intake. The gas thermal properties in the bottom section of the combustor and gasifier are little impacted by the heat carrier size distribution. Klimanek et al (2018) developed two CFD models of CO₂-enhanced coal gasification in pressurized circulating fluidized bed reactor and applied to simulate the process and predict syngas composition at the reactor outlet. The two distinct gasification modeling techniques utilized in this investigation were previously employed to model coal gasification using air and steam/air mixtures. The case studies under investigation demonstrated that adding CO₂ to the gasifying agent in a pressurized fluidized reactor can raise the CO output per unit mass of feedstock, lowering the process's oxygen need. Co-gasification of biomass and fossil fuels provides the best means of increasing the selectivity of gas production and the efficiency of energy use. However, little is known about how fuel and bed material interact inside the co-gasifier or how gas and solids interact while operating at high temperatures and pressures (Sun et al., 2024). To simulate the steam co-gasification of continuous coal and biomass feedstock within a pilot-scale bubbling fluidized bed, a reactive Eulerian-Lagrangian model is built. The findings show that the gasifier's improper surface velocity causes inadequate mixing and excessive entrainment of fuel feedstocks. As the feeding height increases from 80 mm to 200 mm, the mixing index falls from 0.364 to 0.322. Shao et al. (2025) used This study used a two-dimensional (2D) reactive multiphase particle-in-cell (MP-PIC) model to simulate a 15MWth KEDA® circulating fluidized bed (KEDA®CFB) coal gasifier and volatile cracking tests to establish the pyrolysis kinetics. From the perspectives of flow hydrodynamics, thermochemical properties, species distributions, higher heating value (HHV), and cold gas efficiency (CGE), the effects of preheating temperature were investigated. The efficiency of gasification has been discovered to be directly and significantly impacted by the preheating temperature. The HHV (5.55–6.28 MJ/Nm³) and CGE (61–74.7%) significantly rise when the preheating temperature is raised from 400 K to 1300 K. The simulations guide the investigation of technological economy and may be used to optimize the development of gasifiers. Wang et al. (2023) numerically analysed the influence of coal size in the performance and slag flow characterisation of gasifier. The volume average rate of C + CO₂ decreases from 0.0095 to 0.0035 kmol/m³s and C + H₂O increases from 0.0064 to 0.012 kmol/m³s at the first stage, according to the results, as coal size increases from 10 µm to 320 µm. The carbon conversion efficiency at the first stage drops from 99.72% to 93.42%, while it increases from 65% to 93% at the second stage. The formation of slag in the gasifier is not significantly impacted by the increase in coal size with values less than 80 µm. The development of slag is significantly facilitated by increasing coal size, which causes the solid and liquid slag at the slag tap hole to thicken more quickly. For the first stage, a coal size of less than 80 µm may be ideal, while for the second stage, a suitable increase in coal size is advantageous for increasing carbon conversion efficiency.

2 NUMERICAL METHOD

2.1 Modelling

In the present study, the geometry is designed in ANSYS Fluent 2021 R1 academic version software. The geometry is divided into 6 parts as shown in fig 1. The details of the dimension are mentioned in Table 1.

Figure 1. Geometry Design using workbench.

Table 1. Details of Dimensions.

Dimension Line	Length (mm)
H31	1057.5
V33	6737.6
V7	2900
H9	1655
H18	897.32
V17	1136.5
H27	2500
V26	1050
D3	200
D4	300

2.2 Governing Equation

Currently, a three-dimensional, viscous-k-e model with standard wall function is used for numerical analysis. Consequently, time-averaged pressure-based steady-state Equations for Navier-Stokes, mass momentum, energy, and species have been resolved. The following chemical species are used to represent the various reaction mechanisms: C(s), O₂, N₂, CO, CO₂, H₂O, H₂, and volatiles. Volumetric and particle surface type reaction was selected for the species transport model, and the rate of production for each species has been calculated using the Finite Rate/Eddy Dissipation Rate model, which also updates the source term S_r in the governing equations (Wang et al., 2017).

$$S_r = M_j \sum_{j=1}^N W_{j,r} \quad (1)$$

Continuity Equation-

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (2)$$

Where U, V, and W are the velocity components of x, y, and z direction, respectively.

Momentum Equation-

$$\rho \frac{D\vec{v}}{Dt} = -\vec{\nabla}p + \rho\vec{g} + \mu\nabla^2\vec{v} \quad (3)$$

Where $\rho \frac{D\vec{v}}{Dt}$ represent the total derivative, $\vec{\nabla}p$ is the pressure gradient, $\rho\vec{g}$ is the body force term and $\mu\nabla^2\vec{v}$ is the diffusive term.

Energy Equation-

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho E) + \nabla(\rho E \vec{v}) = \nabla(k_{eff} \Delta T) + S_h \quad (4)$$

Gas Phase Reaction-

Table 2. Properties of coal.

Proximate Analysis (W/%)		Ultimate Analysis (W/%)	
Volatile	0.5	C	0.85
Fixed Carbon	0.3	H	0.1
Ash	1	O	0.4
Moisture	1	N	0.01
Volatile Molecular Weight (kg/kg mol)		30	

2.3 Grid Independence Test

Ansys Fluent divides the computational domain into a network of control volumes, or cells. The mesh quality has a significant impact on the solution's accuracy and convergence. Tetrahedral mesh is produced by the pre-processor with good results. To verify that the mesh size has no discernible effect on the correctness of the solution, the grid independence test is necessary. From 0.5mm to 2mm, the mesh's element size (also known as face sizing) was methodically improved. There are 58783 elements and 22487 nodes in the computational domain. The pressure drop is not significantly affected by increasing the mesh elements above these numbers. Additionally, the highest temperature doesn't change.

2.4 Processing and Simulation

The ANSYS FLUENT 2021 R1 Academic Version software is used in this work to simulate CFD. Once the geometry is complete, the next stage is meshing (Fig 2), which involves making meshes. It is an important phase in the simulation's subsequent stages. Many meshing techniques are made possible by the software. Table 3 lists details for the mesh grid.

Table 3. Details of Dimensions.

SI No.	Parameters	Details
1	Physics preference	CFD
2	Solver Preference	Fluent
3	Element Order	Linear
4	Nodes	22633
5	Elements	58712

Figure 2. Meshed Geometry.

Table 4. Basic Operating Condition.

SI No.	Parameters	Details
1	Air mass flowrate (kg/s)	2
2	Coal mass flowrate (kg/s)	1
3	Initial Temperature (K)	300
4	Method	SIMPLE

2.5 Result

After the simulation was completed, the mole fractions, temperature, velocity, and particle flow regimes of coal emerged from the top exhaust. Figure 3 and 4 show the mole fraction contour of CO₂ and H₂O respectively.

Figure 3. CO₂ mole fraction contour

Figure 4. H₂O Mole fraction contour

The gasifier has noticed the temperature rise—figure 5 shows the temperature contour obtained by simulation. The O₂ mole fraction contour is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Temperature contour

Figure 6. O₂ Mole fraction contour

Figure 7. Velocity Streamline

Figure 8. Mole Fraction of Volatile

3 CONCLUSIONS

In this present study, a numerical model of a combustor is developed. The reaction mechanism and stoichiometry were produced from the coal calculator by the proximal and ultimate input of the feed given, and the species transport model in Fluent was used by combining all the zones of the combustor. However, by changing the reaction and substituting for the standard gasifier reaction, this research will set a precedent for simulating a gasifier. Numerous proximate and ultimate analyses derived from various feeds and biomass can be assigned.

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